

1 **Combined effects of warming and acidification on accumulation and elimination**
2 **dynamics of paralytic shellfish toxins in mussels *Mytilus galloprovincialis***

3

4 Ana C. Braga^{1,2}, Carolina Camacho¹, António Marques^{1,3}, Ana Gago-Martínez⁴, Mário
5 Pacheco², Pedro R. Costa^{1,5*}

6

7 ¹ IPMA - Portuguese Institute for the Sea and Atmosphere, Av. Brasília, 1449-006
8 Lisbon, Portugal

9 ² Biology Department and CESAM, Aveiro University, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

10 ³ Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research (CIIMAR), University
11 of Porto, Rua dos Bragas, 289, 4050-123 Porto, Portugal

12 ⁴ Universidad de Vigo, Department of Analytical and Food Chemistry, Campus
13 Universitario de Vigo, 36310-Vigo, Spain

14 ⁵ CCMAR – Centre of Marine Sciences, University of Algarve, Campus of Gambelas,
15 8005-139 Faro, Portugal

16

17 * Corresponding author Telf: +351 213027169; E-mail: prcosta@ipma.pt

18

19

20

21

22

23

24 Abstract

25 Harmful algal blooms (HAB) have been increasing in frequency and intensity most
26 likely due to changes on global conditions, which constitute a significant threat to wild
27 shellfish and its commercial farming. This study evaluated the impact of increasing
28 seawater temperature and acidification on the accumulation/elimination dynamics of
29 HAB-toxins in shellfish. *Mytilus galloprovincialis* were acclimated to four
30 environmental conditions simulating different climate change scenarios: *i*) current
31 conditions, *ii*) warming, *iii*) acidification and *iv*) interaction of warming with
32 acidification. Once acclimated, mussels were exposed to the paralytic shellfish toxins
33 (PSTs) producing dinoflagellate *Gymnodinium catenatum* for 5 days and to non-toxic
34 diet during the subsequent 10 days. High toxicity levels (1493 $\mu\text{g STX eq kg}^{-1}$)
35 exceeding the safety limits were determined under current conditions at the end of the
36 uptake period. Significantly lower PSP toxicity levels were registered for warming- and
37 acidification-acclimated mussels (661 and 761 $\mu\text{g STX eq kg}^{-1}$). The combined effect of
38 both warming and acidification resulted in PSP toxicity values slightly higher (856 μg
39 STX eq kg^{-1}). A rapid decrease of toxicity was observed in mussels at the current
40 conditions after shifting to a non-toxic diet, which was not noticed under the predicted
41 climate change scenarios. Variability of each PST analogue, measured throughout the
42 experiment, highlighted different mechanisms are associated with changes of each
43 environmental factor, although both resulting in lower toxicity. Warming-acclimated
44 mussels showed lower accumulation/elimination rates, while acidification-acclimated
45 mussels showed higher capability to accumulate toxins, but also a higher elimination
46 rate preventing high toxicity levels. As different mechanisms are triggered by warming
47 and acidification, their combined effect not leads to a synergism of their individual
48 effects. The present work is the first assessing the combined effect of climate change

49 drivers on accumulation/elimination of PSTs, in mussels, indicating that warming and
50 acidification may lead to lower toxicity values but longer toxic episodes. PSTs are
51 responsible for the food poisoning syndrome, paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) in
52 humans. This study can be considered as the first step to build models for predicting
53 shellfish toxicity under climate change scenarios.

54

55 Keywords: Harmful algal blooms; Climate change; Seafood safety; saxitoxins; *Gymnodinium*
56 *catenatum*.

57

58 1. Introduction

59

60 Most coastal areas are highly productive and simultaneously vulnerable ecosystems
61 that have been continuously affected by multiple man-made pressures. The impacts of
62 climate change are likely to deteriorate environmental conditions and worsen ecological
63 problems in these sensitive coastal ecosystems, where bivalves play a significant role.
64 Bivalves are of high ecological importance, increasing local biomass, promoting
65 biodiversity, and being responsible for some ecosystem engineering processes (Sousa et
66 al., 2009, Fernández-Reiriz *et al.*, 2012). In addition, these molluscs are an import
67 source of protein for human consumption, representing valuable resources for coastal
68 populations.

69 Warming, sea level rise, changes on circulation and salinity patterns, nutrient and
70 sediment regimes, and acidification have been pointed out as the major climate change
71 drivers affecting coastal areas (Filgueira et al., 2016). The Intergovernmental Panel on
72 Climate Change (IPCC) indicates that, not only, the water temperature increased in the
73 last century, but also acidification occurred, with a decrease of the water pH by almost
74 0.6 pH units (IPCC, 2013). These trends are projected to worsen, with temperatures

75 increasing over 4.5 degrees Celsius and pH decreasing from 0.3 to 0.5 pH units by 2100
76 in the worst case scenarios (IPCC, 2013). While IPCC values are projected for the end
77 of the century, global ocean conditions, coastal areas and intertidal organisms, such as
78 shellfish, are nowadays being frequently challenged with abrupt changes of
79 environmental conditions (Filgueira et al., 2016).

80 Thermal tolerance with changing temperatures has been the focus of several studies
81 (Pörtner et al., 2007). The increase of temperature usually leads to an increase in
82 feeding and metabolic rates, promoting growth and reproduction when values are within
83 the species thermal optimum range and in the presence of sufficient food and oxygen
84 (Filgueira et al., 2016). However, when these conditions are not met, the increase in
85 temperature may negatively affect shellfish. Changes in mussels behaviour, immune
86 response, standard metabolic rate, reduction of energy available for the somatic
87 metabolism, and negative impacts on growth rates have been associated with increasing
88 temperature (Anestis et al., 2007; Coppola et al., 2017; Múgica et al., 2015). Increase of
89 temperature may also promote the uptake, accumulation and metabolization of some
90 pollutants, like metals (e.g. Ni and Cd) and radionuclides, as well as persistent organic
91 pollutants (POPs) and methylmercury (Alava et al., 2017; Banni et al., 2014; Coppola et
92 al., 2017; Dallas et al., 2016; Múgica et al., 2015; Sokolova and Lannig, 2008).
93 Regarding marine biotoxins, namely paralytic shellfish poisoning toxins, temperature
94 increase seems to affect their accumulation and elimination reducing both in oysters
95 (Farrell *et al.*, 2015) and increasing elimination surf clams (Bricelj et al., 2014).

96 In coastal upwelling zones, such as the Iberian Peninsula, the west coast of
97 Americas, and the northwest and southwest coast of Africa, ocean acidification is
98 anticipated to rise with the intensification of upwelling regimes (Bakun et al., 2015).
99 Prolonged exposure to hypercapnia (acidified waters) may decrease the inter- and extra-

100 cellular pH values and the consequent shell dissolution to compensate these acid-base
101 disturbances (Parker et al., 2013). It also leads to changes in several physiological and
102 metabolic processes like the reduction of thermal tolerance, decreased O₂ consumption,
103 increased standard metabolic rates (SMR) and reduction of somatic growth rates
104 (Michaelidis et al., 2005; Nikinmaa and Anttila, 2015; Parker et al., 2013).

105 The eastern boundary upwelling systems are among the most productive marine
106 ecosystems. The nutrient pulses from deeper waters into the coastal photic zone, often
107 resulting in phytoplankton blooms that are the basis of the marine food web. Among
108 phytoplankton species blooming, some produce toxins as secondary metabolites, which
109 are then accumulated in the biota, particularly by filter-feeding bivalves, and can
110 become a public health concern. Recently, the largest and longest harmful *Pseudo-*
111 *nitzschia* diatom bloom was observed along the west coast of the US associated with
112 anomalously warming ocean conditions, being the bloom sustained by upwelled
113 nutrients from the seasonal spring transition (Bond et al., 2015; McCabe et al., 2016).
114 On the other hand, based on data from the last three decades, Pérez *et al.* (2010) pointed
115 out a decline of coastal upwelling in the inner shelf of the Iberian Peninsula induced by
116 sea surface warming. The upwelling decline and consequent less turbulent environment
117 and persistence of stratified conditions may result in an increase in the frequency of
118 toxic dinoflagellates blooms, such as *Dinophysis* spp. and *Gymnodinium catenatum*,
119 profoundly impacting shellfisheries (Vidal et al 2017). The bloom-forming
120 dinoflagellates *Dinophysis* spp. and *G. catenatum* are linked to diarrhetic shellfish
121 poisoning (DSP) and paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) outbreaks in humans,
122 respectively. *G. catenatum* produces highly potent neurotoxins designated as paralytic
123 shellfish toxins (PSTs). Its life-cycle includes a microreticulate resting cysts stage that
124 facilitates their widespread distribution, either promoted by changes in natural

125 conditions or by anthropogenic activities (Hallegraeff et al., 2012, Gobler et al., 2017).
126 Harmful algal blooms (HAB), including *G. catenatum*-blooms, seem to be emerging
127 and expanding in recent decades, which negatively affects the marine ecosystems and
128 local economies due to increasing closures to shellfish harvesting (Gobler et al., 2017).

129 Research on the combined effects of warming seawater and acidification and
130 exposure to harmful algal blooms on a bivalve production context is still scarce.
131 Therefore, this study aims to assess the impact of both relevant climate change drivers
132 *per se* and their combined effect on the dynamics of PSTs accumulation and elimination
133 in *Mytilus galloprovincialis*.

134

135 2. Material and methods

136 2.1. Mussel collection and acclimation

137

138 One hundred and twenty immature Mediterranean mussels, *Mytilus*
139 *galloprovincialis* (53.78 ± 6.22 mm), were harvested in Aveiro Lagoon in July 2016,
140 when blooms of *G. catenatum* were not occurring. Upon collection, mussels were
141 immediately shipped to IPMA facilities (Lisbon) in a thermally isolated container.
142 Mussels were cleaned from macro-algae, barnacles or any other epibiont, and placed in
143 four 150 L tank systems, subdivided into 6 replicates. Each tank systems was equipped
144 with a protein skimmer (Reef SkimPro, TMC Iberia, Portugal), UV disinfection (Vecton
145 300, TMC Iberia, Portugal), biological filtration (model FSBF 1500, TMC Iberia,
146 Portugal) and chemical filtration (activated carbon, Fernando Ribeiro Lda, Portugal) to
147 maintain seawater quality. Each tank was used to simulate a specific treatment: 1 -
148 current conditions (Tr1: 19 °C; pH 8.0), 2 - warming (Tr2: 24 °C; pH 8.0), 3 -
149 acidification (Tr3: 19 °C; pH 7.6) and 4 - warming and acidification (Tr4: 24 °C; pH

150 7.6) (Fig. 1). The seawater used was filtered (0.35 μm) and UV sterilised. Mussels were
151 gradually adapted to the conditions of each treatment, by increasing 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and decreasing
152 0.1 pH units per day. The animals were then acclimatised for 21 days, being fed with
153 non-toxic and freeze-dried *Tetraselmis sp.* diet (Necton, Olhão, Portugal). Temperature
154 and pH were automatically adjusted whenever needed. Water temperature was cooled
155 through an automatic seawater refrigeration system (± 0.1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; Frimar, Fernando Ribeiro
156 Lda, Portugal) or heated by submerged digital heaters (200W, V2Therm, TMC Iberia,
157 Portugal). Water pH was measured through individual pH probes (GHL, Germany)
158 connected to a computerized pH control system (± 0.1 pH units; Profilux 3.1N, GHL,
159 Germany), which monitored each tank every 2 s, and adjusted them whenever need, via
160 submerged air stones, by injecting CO_2 (Air Liquide, Portugal; to decrease pH) or
161 filtered air (to increase pH) using air pumps (Stella 200, Aqua One Pro, Aqua Pacific
162 UK Ltd, United Kingdom).

163 Tanks were kept under the following abiotic conditions: i) dissolved oxygen (DO) >
164 5 mg L^{-1} ; ii) salinity = 35.7 ± 0.4 ‰; iii) photoperiod = 12L:12D (12 hours light:12
165 hours dark). Temperature, pH, salinity and DO were daily checked using a multi-
166 parameter measuring instrument (Multi 3420 SET G, WTW, Germany). Ammonia,
167 nitrite and nitrate levels were daily checked by means of colorimetric tests (Tropic
168 Marin, USA), and kept below detectable levels with daily water changes, except
169 nitrates, which were kept below 2.0 mg L^{-1} . Seawater total alkalinity was also measured
170 in every tank on a weekly basis, spectrophotometrically at 595 nm, following a protocol
171 previously described elsewhere (Sarazin et al., 1999) and the combination of total
172 alkalinity (AT) and pH was used to calculate carbonate system parameters. A summary
173 of seawater parameters is reported in Table A.1 and Figure A.1 of Appendix A.

174

175 Figure 1. Design of mussels feeding experiments with toxic dinoflagellates *Gymnodinium catenatum*
 176 under four environmental conditions (Tr1: 19 °C and 8.0 pH; Tr2: 24 °C and 8.0 pH; Tr3: 19 °C and 7.6
 177 pH; Tr4: 24 °C and 7.6 pH), showing sampling dates during uptake (grey) and elimination (white) phases.
 178

179 2.2. *Gymnodinium catenatum* cultivation

180

181 *G. catenatum* strain IO-13-04, obtained from the algae culture collection at Lisbon
 182 University (ALISU), was isolated from a bloom in Espinho, NW Portuguese coast, in
 183 September 2005. Cells were mass cultured in 2 L flasks with seawater adjusted to 30 %
 184 and enriched with GSe medium as in Doblin *et al.* (1999) without the soil extract.
 185 Seawater and nutrients solutions were filtered and autoclaved to minimise
 186 contamination. The cultures were grown at 18 °C with a 12:12 L:D cycle under
 187 fluorescent lights. Cells were harvested when cultures presented a density of
 188 approximately 2.5×10^6 cells per litre, concentrated using 10 µm mesh sieve. The toxin

189 profile of the algae was composed by sulfocarbamoyl toxins and decarbamoyl toxins
190 (Table 1). Toxins were determined in the algae cell culture as described below (section
191 2.4).

192

193 Table 1. PST content and toxin profile of the *Gymnodinium catenatum* culture used to feed mussels.

Toxin	Concentration (fmol.cell⁻¹)	Molar Fraction (%)
C1+2	40.80	95.7
GTX5	1.01	2.4
dcNeo	0.42	1.0
dcGTX2+3	0.31	0.7
dcSTX	0.1	0.2
C3+4	*	*
GTX6	*	*

194 * - Not Quantified

195

196 2.3. Mussels exposure to toxic dinoflagellates

197

198 During acclimation, mussels were fed with 100,000 cells per day per animal of the
199 non-toxic and freeze-dried, *Tetraselmis* sp. diet (Necton, Olhão, Portugal). The mussels
200 were then fed for 5 days with toxic dinoflagellates from a *G. catenatum* culture under
201 the conditions indicated in the previous section and following the experimental design
202 shown in figure 1. Mussels were exposed to approximately 91,000 *G. catenatum* cells
203 per day per animal. After the 5 days of exposure to the toxic diet, mussels were fed

204 again with 100,000 cells per day per animal of *Tetraselmis* sp. during 10 days in order
205 to assess the elimination of toxins accumulated during the 5-days exposure period. Two
206 mussels exposed to *G. catenatum* were collected in triplicate for toxin analysis on days
207 1 and 5, corresponding to the uptake period, and on days 6, 10 and 15, corresponding to
208 the elimination period.

209

210 2.4. Determination of PSTs

211 2.4.1. Reagents

212

213 All reagents used for toxins extraction and analysis were of analytical grade or
214 higher. Acetic acid glacial (100%, p.a.), methanol (> 99.8%, p.a.) and acetonitrile
215 (Analytical grade) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich; ammonium formate (> 99%
216 purity) from Fluka; Hydrochloric acid (37%) from Panreac; Hydrogen peroxide (30%)
217 and sodium hydroxide (> 99%, p.a.) from Merck. Water was purified using a Milli-Q
218 185 Plus system from Millipore. Toxins standard solutions for dcGTX2 + 3, C1 + 2,
219 dcSTX, GTX2 + 3, GTX5 and STX, were purchased from the Certified Reference
220 Materials Program of the Institute for Marine Biosciences, National Research Council
221 (NRC, Canada).

222

223 2.4.2. Extraction and determination of PSTs by liquid chromatography with 224 Fluorescence detection

225

226 Extraction of toxins from *G. catenatum* cell cultures followed the methodology
227 described by Silva *et al.* (2015). Briefly, an aliquot of *G. catenatum* cell culture (500

228 mL) was filtered onto 47 mm Whatman GF/C with a nominal pore size of 1.2 mm,
229 under low vacuum. Toxins were extracted in 4 mL of 0.05 M acetic acid and sonicated
230 for 4 min at 25 Watts, 50% pulse duty cycle (Vibracell, Sonic & Materials, Newtown,
231 CT, USA) in an ice bath. Cell lysis was confirmed with light microscopy. The extract
232 was then centrifuged (3000 g) for 10 min, and 1 mL of the supernatant was used for the
233 determination of PSTs. The supernatant was cleaned by solid-phase extraction (SPE)
234 with an octadecyl bonded phase silica (Supelclean LC-18 SPE cartridge, 3 mL, Supelco,
235 USA). Briefly, the SPE cartridge was conditioned with 6 mL of methanol, followed by
236 6 mL of water and 1 mL of extract was loaded to the cartridge and the PSTs eluted with
237 2 mL of water.

238 Both extraction of toxins from mussels and the determination of the PSTs followed
239 the EU reference method (AOAC Official Method 2005.06) which consists on a Liquid
240 chromatographic separation coupled to fluorescence detection (LC-FLD) with
241 precolumn derivatization, to convert the toxins into the correspondent fluorescent
242 derivatives. Briefly, 5 g of shellfish whole soft tissue homogenate was double extracted
243 with 1% acetic acid solution (first extraction with heating), and the extracts were
244 cleaned using solid-phase SPE C18 cartridge (Supelclean, Supelco, USA). Before
245 LC/FLD analysis, 100 µl of C18 extract from both algae and mussels was derivatized
246 with peroxide and periodate oxidants.

247 LC-FLD analysis were performed on a Hewlett-Packard/Agilent LC system
248 (Germany) constituted by a Model 1100 quaternary pump, Model 1100 in-line degasser,
249 autosampler, column oven, and Model 1200 fluorescence detector. The Hewlett-Packard
250 Chemstation software performed data acquisition and peak integration. Toxins
251 separation was performed using a reversed-phase column Supelcosil C18 column 150 x
252 4.6 mm id, 5 µm (Supelco, USA) equipped with a column Supelguard Supelcosil C18,

253 20 mm id x 4.0 mm id, 5 μm (Supelco, USA) and kept in a column oven at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The
254 flow rate was 1 mL min^{-1} and the mobile phase gradient used to elute the PSTs
255 oxidation products consisted of 2 mobile phases under the following conditions: 0–5%
256 B (0.1 M ammonium formate in 5% acetonitrile, $\text{pH} = 6$) in the first 5 min, 5–70% B for
257 the following 4 min and 100% mobile phase A (0.1 M ammonium formate, $\text{pH} = 6$)
258 used during 5 min before the next injection. The injection volume was 50 μL , detection
259 wavelengths were set at 340 nm for excitation and 395 nm for emission. PSTs were
260 identified by comparison with standards retention times and quantified by interpolation
261 in the calibration curves obtained with the factor response peak areas *vs.* toxin
262 concentration (see an illustrative LC-FLD chromatogram of PSTs in Appendix A.
263 Figure A.2). The limits of detection (signal-to-noise ratio of 3) ranged from 0.004 μM
264 for C1 + 2, GTX5 and STX to 0.020 μM for dcNEO. The toxicity equivalent factors
265 stated by EFSA (2009) were used for calculation of PSTs in terms of saxitoxin
266 equivalents. The total PSP toxicity in the sample corresponds to the sum of all toxin
267 analogs quantified. For toxins co-eluting and determined together (C1 + 2, dcGTX2 + 3,
268 and GTX2 + 3) the higher toxicity equivalent factor of the co-eluted compound was
269 used. Low potency PSTs analogues for which analytical standards were not available,
270 namely C3+4 and GTX6, were not considered for this study.

271

272 2.4.3. Statistics

273

274 Two-Way Analysis of Variance followed by a Multiple Comparisons *versus* Control
275 Group (Bonferroni t-test) was used to assess significant differences on toxin content and
276 toxicity between the current conditions, warming, acidification and the combined effect
277 of warming and acidification. Also, a Two-Way Analysis of Variance followed by All

278 Pairwise Multiple Comparison Procedures (Bonferroni t-test) was used to assess
279 significant differences between the sampling dates.

280 For the empirical kinetics of PSTs elimination, a one-compartment model was used
281 to describe elimination kinetics using a single component first-order kinetic model:

$$282 \quad \frac{dC_m}{dt} = -k_{el} C_m \quad (1)$$

283 where C_m is the toxin concentration in mussels and k_{el} denotes the elimination rate.

284 Solving this differential equation gives:

$$285 \quad C_m = C_{m0} e^{-k_{el} t} \quad (2)$$

286 The toxin concentration decreases according to an exponential decay, with the
287 steepness of the decay being determined by the elimination rate (k) and the size of the
288 curve depending of the initial concentration of the toxin (C_{m0}) at the beginning of the
289 elimination period, when mussels diet was changed from *G. catenatum* to non-toxic
290 algae.

291 Data were tested for normality and homogeneity of variance by the Kolmogorov-
292 Smirnov test and the Levene Median test. Differences were considered significant at $p <$
293 0.05. Data analysis was performed using the statistical program SigmaPlot Version
294 10.0.

295

296 3. Results

297 3.1. Impact of warming and acidification on mussels toxicity

298

299 A marked increase of PSTs accumulation was observed in mussels during the uptake
300 period in all treatments (Fig. 2). The highest toxin levels were determined in mussels at
301 the current conditions of temperature and pH (Tr1: 19 °C and pH 8), which in terms of
302 shellfish toxicity expressed as saxitoxin equivalents after multiplying the toxins
303 concentration with the respective toxicity factor, reached levels of $1,493.8 \pm 202.4 \mu\text{g}$
304 STX eq. kg^{-1} at day 5. PSP toxicity was significantly ($p < 0.001$) lower in acidification-
305 and warming-acclimated mussels, reaching values of 761.2 ± 62.3 and $661.9 \pm 22.8 \mu\text{g}$
306 STX eq. kg^{-1} , respectively. Although similar to the toxicity observed for treatments 2
307 and 3, where the effect of each climate change driver was evaluated individually, the
308 combined effect of both components, tested in treatment 4, resulted in PSP toxicity
309 values slightly higher ($855.8 \pm 61.4 \mu\text{g STX eq. kg}^{-1}$).

310 When algae provided to mussels was changed to non-toxic species, a decrease of
311 toxicity was immediately observed in all treatments. The decrease of PSP toxicity was
312 particularly evident in mussels at current conditions. For these mussels, a significant
313 decrease ($p < 0.001$) was observed after 24 hours feeding on non-toxic algae,
314 corresponding to a toxicity reduction of $57.4 \pm 3.2 \%$. The highest toxicity decrease in
315 the first 24 hours was found in acidification treatment ($66.9 \pm 5.0 \%$), and the lowest
316 decrease of only $27.3 \pm 12.9 \%$ was registered for mussels maintained in the warming
317 treatment. The interaction between the two variables conducted to a decrease of $47.6 \pm$
318 25.7% . Toxicity reached similar levels for all treatments in the subsequent days of the
319 elimination period (Fig. 2).

320

321

322 Figure 2. PSP toxicity ($\mu\text{g STX eq. kg}^{-1}$, mean \pm SD) determined in mussels exposed to toxic
 323 *Gymnodinium catenatum* during 5 days and to non-toxic diet during the subsequent 10 days, under four
 324 environmental conditions (Tr1: 19 °C and 8.0 pH; Tr2: 24 °C and 8.0 pH; Tr3: 19 °C and 7.6 pH; Tr4: 24
 325 °C and 7.6 pH)

326

327 3.2. Accumulation and elimination kinetics of PSTs under conditions of warming 328 and acidification

329

330 The profile of PSTs detected in mussels, as illustrated in figure 3, was constituted by
 331 the same toxins found in the toxic algae given as food, namely C1+2, GTX5,
 332 dcGTX2+3, dcSTX and dcNeo.

333 At the end of the 5-day uptake period, significantly higher concentrations of each
 334 PST congener were observed in mussels acclimated at current conditions than in the
 335 other treatments. Exception occurred for the concentration of C1+2, which was
 336 determined at levels similarly high in mussels at current (Tr1) and acidified (Tr3)
 337 conditions.

338

339 Figure 3. Concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, mean \pm SD) of PSTs (C1+2, GTX5, dcNeo, dcGTX2+3 and
 340 dcSTX) determined in mussels exposed to *Gymnodinium catenatum* at day 1 (white bars) and 5 (black
 341 bars), under four environmental conditions (Tr1: 19 °C and 8.0 pH; Tr2: 24 °C and 8.0 pH; Tr3: 19 °C and
 342 7.6 pH; Tr4: 24 °C and 7.6 pH). Values marked with an asterisk represent significant differences ($p <$
 343 0.05) from current conditions (vs. Tr1) within the same exposure time.

344

345 Significant differences in concentration of PSTs were also found between the
 346 combined effect of warming and acidification (Tr4) with each component tested
 347 individually (Tr2 or Tr3). Indeed, higher C1+2 concentrations were determined in Tr4
 348 than in Tr2, but reaching lower levels than in Tr3. Higher GTX5 and dcSTX
 349 concentrations were determined in Tr4 than in Tr2 and Tr3. Finally, concentrations of
 350 dcGTX2+3 reached lower values than Tr2, but not statistically different to Tr3.

351 After reaching the peak of toxins accumulation in day 5, the shift to non-toxic
 352 diet resulted in a decrease of toxins concentrations. However, toxins were not
 353 completely eliminated during the studied period (10 days). The timeline of toxins
 354 elimination in each treatment is illustrated in figure 4. All toxins fitted well to an
 355 exponential decay model, except dcGTX2+3. Elimination rates calculated from the best
 356 fit are indicated in table 2. The highest elimination rates were generally obtained for
 357 mussels under acidifying conditions, and lower elimination rates were registered in
 358 mussels under warming conditions. The combination of both climate change drivers
 359 resulted in an attenuation of effects, leading to elimination rates between mussels at
 360 current and acidified conditions.

361

362 Table 2. Elimination rate (k_{el} , d^{-1}) (\pm standard error) and coefficient of determination R^2 of each PST
 363 determined in mussels under four environmental conditions (Tr1: 19 °C and 8.0 pH; Tr2: 24 °C and 8.0
 364 pH; Tr3: 19 °C and 7.6 pH; Tr4: 24 °C and 7.6 pH).

Treatment	Toxin	Elimination Rate	R²
Tr1 Current Conditions	C1+2	0.173 (\pm 0.052)*	0.81
	GTX5	0.131 (\pm 0.035)*	0.82
	dcNeo	0.578 (\pm 0.076)*	0.98
	dcSTX	0.234 (\pm 0.071)*	0.82
Tr2 Warming	C1+2	0.087 (\pm 0.016)*	0.89
	GTX5	0.074 (\pm 0.024)*	0.73
	dcNeo	0.300 (\pm 0.037)*	0.98
	dcSTX	0.105 (\pm 0.018)*	0.90
Tr3 Acidification	C1+2	0.898 (\pm 0.219)*	0.93
	GTX5	0.063 (\pm 0.027)*	0.63

	dcNeo	0.658 (\pm 0.243)*	0.90
	dcSTX	0.231 (\pm 0.064)*	0.85
Tr4	C1+2	0.355 (\pm 0.114)*	0.86
Warming	GTX5	0.064 (\pm 0.021)*	0.71
and	dcNeo	0.904 (\pm 0.194)*	0.95
Acidification	dcSTX	0.174 (\pm 0.062)*	0.73

365

366 * Represents values within the confidence limit ($P < 0.05$).

367

368

369 C1+2, that were initially the dominant PSTs found in algae and mussels from the
370 four treatments, was easily eliminated in mussels maintained in acidification conditions.
371 On the other hand, these toxins were slowly eliminated from mussels under warming
372 conditions. The lowest elimination rates were calculated for GTX5 in all treatments.
373 The most potent compound from this set of toxins, *i.e.* dcSTX, was rapidly eliminated
374 in mussels under current conditions compared to any other treatment.

375

376

377

378 Figure 4. Elimination of the PSTs (C1+2, dcSTX, GTX5, dcNeo and dcGTX2+3) in mussels under four
 379 environmental conditions (Tr1: 19 °C and 8.0 pH; Tr2: 24 °C and 8.0 pH; Tr3: 19 °C and 7.6 pH; Tr4: 24
 380 °C and 7.6 pH). Dots and error bars represent experimental data; the coloured lines represent the output of
 381 the simulation model ($C_m = C_{m0} e^{-k_{el}t}$).

382

383 4. Discussion

384

385 Climate change is a complex phenomenon, resulting from alterations on several
 386 environmental drivers. Temperature might be the easiest parameter to follow, but
 387 climate changes include several other parameters with direct and indirect impact on pH,
 388 salinity, oxygen levels, current regimes and even frequency and intensity of harmful
 389 algal blooms (HAB). Therefore, it is essential to understand the interaction of these

390 variables, which may lead to either antagonistic or synergistic responses of marine
391 organisms (Duarte et al., 2014; Lischka et al., 2011).

392 HAB-toxins represent a significant threat to commercial shellfish farming,
393 frequently leading to closures to harvesting due to toxins accumulation at levels above
394 the international regulatory limits. In this study, mussels feeding during 5 days on PSTs-
395 producing dinoflagellate *Gymnodinium catenatum* exceeded the EU regulatory limit of
396 800 $\mu\text{g STX eq. kg}^{-1}$ when maintained under the current conditions of temperature and
397 pH and in the combined acidification and warming conditions. In contrast, mussels
398 acclimated solely to warming and acidification displayed significantly lower PSP
399 toxicity levels, i.e. below but close to the safety limits. Seafood demand has grown in
400 the last decades and is expected to increase at a higher level with the global population
401 growth. For this reason, sustainable increased production, *i.e.* aquaculture, is seen as the
402 solution to meet the demand for shellfish that cannot be supported by the declining wild
403 stocks. According to PSP toxicity results in this study, one could suggest that climate
404 change, regarding warming and acidification, may benefit shellfisheries as lower
405 toxicity levels are reached. Nevertheless, the decrease of toxicity during the elimination
406 period was significantly slower in acclimated mussels than in mussels maintained at
407 current environmental conditions. Assuming that HAB are increasing in frequency and
408 intensity (Fu et al., 2012) and that toxin-producing dinoflagellates under acidified
409 conditions are prone to increase their toxicity (Tatters et al., 2013), shellfish are
410 expected to become more frequently contaminated. Moreover, shellfish may remain
411 contaminated for longer periods, although not reaching the actual exacerbated levels.

412 Most studies on climate change effects in shellfish have focused on a single driver
413 (*e.g.* temperature, acidification, salinity) (Anestis et al., 2010, 2007; Farrell et al., 2015;
414 Fernández-Reiriz et al., 2012). A reduced number of studies addressed the combination

415 of two variables. In this study, the individual impact of each parameter was tested to
416 better understand the effects of their interaction. Analyzing warming as a single climate
417 change driver in mussels exposed to toxic algae lead to a reduction of toxicity levels.
418 The same trend was previously described by Farrell *et al.* (2015) in one of the few
419 studies combining climate change drivers, namely increased temperature and biotoxin
420 accumulation. A reduction in both accumulation and elimination of the PSTs GTX1+4
421 and GTX2+3 were observed in warming-acclimated oysters fed with toxic *Alexandrium*
422 *minutum*. Reduction of oysters PSP toxicity under warming conditions was not
423 concurrent with decrease of clearance rates and routine metabolism (Farrel *et al.* 2015).
424 In contrast, a reduction of nearly 50 % of clearance rates were reported in mussels *M.*
425 *galloprovincialis* under warming conditions (Anestis *et al.*, 2010). This reduction was
426 suggested to be related with a metabolic depression mechanism in order to balance the
427 increase in energy demand due to warmer water temperatures (Anestis *et al.*, 2010).
428 Although clearance and metabolic rates were not assessed in the present study, lower
429 PSP toxicity values in warming-acclimated mussels may result from changes on these
430 physiological components.

431 In addition to increasing temperature, the effect of acidification was also
432 investigated. Ocean acidification is not plausible without temperature rising. However,
433 to better understand the role of this climate change driver, mussels were acclimated to
434 an acidification scenario with and without warming. Testing this parameter individually
435 also allowed to investigate the hypothesis that lower pH conditions may promote the
436 elimination of PSTs. This hypothesis was raised in 1965, but not positively tested
437 (Hayes, 1966; Shumway *et al.*, 1995). Suspecting that pH could affect shellfish
438 physiology and favor toxins elimination, Hayes (1966) submitted PST contaminated
439 butter clams (*Saxidomus giganteus*) to extreme acidified pH values (5 and 6) for 15

440 hours at 7° C without promising results. In the present study, significant decrease in
441 mussel toxicity was observed, reclaiming this hypothesis as a way to promote PSTs
442 elimination.

443 In the present study, the lower toxicity levels found for *M. galloprovincialis* under
444 acidified conditions appear to be related with different mechanisms than those
445 associated with toxicity reduction at increasing temperatures. *M. galloprovincialis*
446 acclimated to seawater acidification conditions (*i.e.* to pH decrease of 0.3 or 0.6 units)
447 have shown to maintain their clearance, ingestion and metabolic rates (Fernández-Reiriz
448 *et al.*, 2012). Alternatively, some digestive enzymes may present higher activities
449 (Areekijserree *et al.*, 2004; Fernández-Reiriz *et al.*, 2012). Indeed, induction of
450 enzymatic activities and antioxidants was found at a pH around 7.3 and 7.7 (Hu *et al.*,
451 2015). In *M. coruscus*, an increase in the reduced glutathione (GSH) consumption was
452 assessed under acidification conditions (Hu *et al.*, 2015). The consumption of this
453 antioxidant is particularly relevant since GSH has been found to have an important role
454 on biotransformation and elimination of PSTs analogues (Costa *et al.*, 2012; Sakamoto
455 *et al.*, 2000; Sato *et al.*, 2000). Assessing the variability of each PST analogue
456 throughout the experiment was essential to better understand the individual effects of
457 warming and acidification. Although both climate change drivers resulted in lower PSP
458 toxicity levels, the individual effects of warming and acidification differed on the
459 accumulation and elimination of several PST analogues determined.

460 The *N*-sulfocarbamoyl analogues C1+2 were the most abundant toxin congeners
461 found in mussels during the uptake period in all treatments, as they were the most
462 abundant PST identified in the micro-algae. However, C1+2 concentration was
463 significantly higher in mussels maintained under acidification conditions than in
464 warming-acclimated mussels. In fact, the concentration of C1+2 was similar to mussels

465 under current conditions, suggesting high uptake rates and no effects on clearance rates,
466 thus supporting previous findings mentioned above (*i.e.* Fernández-Reiriz *et al.*, 2012).

467 The C1+2 are the least potent of the PST derivatives, making variations in their
468 concentrations less relevant for total PSP toxicity. On the other hand, variability of
469 decarbamoyl toxin analogues, in particular, dcSTX that is the most potent compound of
470 this set of toxins, notably impacts mussels PSP toxicity. The accumulation of these
471 analogues was identically reduced in mussels maintained at either warming or
472 acidification, which was the main factor for decreasing toxicity levels in mussels
473 subjected to climate change drivers compared to mussels at current conditions.

474 The effects of warming and acidification also differed during the elimination period.
475 The experimental data concerning the concentration of toxins determined in mussels
476 during this period fitted well to the dynamic model, providing a good description of the
477 kinetics of C1+2, GTX5, dcNeo and dcSTX in mussels. C1+2 that dominated mussels
478 profile in all treatments are the less stable (Kodama, 2010) and easier eliminated PST
479 derivatives (Botelho *et al.*, 2010; Li *et al.*, 2005; Lopes *et al.*, 2014; Yu *et al.*, 2007).
480 The highest C1+2 elimination rates were calculated in mussels under acidification
481 conditions (Tr3), which highly accumulated these toxins during the uptake period.
482 Mussels of this treatment (Tr3) revealed similar or slightly higher elimination rates of
483 dcSTX and dcNeo than mussels maintained at current environmental conditions. The
484 lowest elimination rate in mussels at Tr3 was calculated for GTX5. Reduced elimination
485 rates of GTX5 were also obtained for warming-acclimated mussels and under the
486 combined effect of warming and acidification. These elimination rates support the
487 theory discussed before referring acidification as a possible way to promote toxins
488 elimination. Despite no clear biotransformation pattern was detected in our study, an
489 enhancement of biotransformation enzymes described under acidified conditions (Hu *et*

490 al., 2015) could be behind these rates. Warming-acclimated mussels presented the
491 lowest or nearly the lowest elimination rates in all toxin congeners, pointing out a
492 decrease in mussels metabolic activity as suggested by Anestis *et al.*(2010).

493 The effects of both climate change drivers, *i.e.* warming and acidification, lead to a
494 reduction of PSP toxicity, but mussels subjected to the combined effect of both drivers
495 showed only slightly higher toxicity levels than mussels subjected solely to warming or
496 acidification. This fact highlights the need for more studies approaching the exposure to
497 multiple climate change drivers.

498

499 5. Conclusion

500

501 The present work is the first study assessing PSTs accumulation and elimination in
502 mussels under the combined effects of warming and acidifying environments, indicating
503 that such climate change scenarios may lead to lower but prolonged PSP contamination
504 in *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. Although the combined effects of warming and
505 acidification promoted lower PSP toxicity levels than the current conditions, the
506 underlying kinetics differed among them. While warming-acclimated mussels
507 accumulated low toxin levels and may retain them due to low elimination rates, mussels
508 at acidification conditions showed higher ability to accumulate PSTs, but their high
509 elimination rates prevented mussels to reach high toxicity levels as mussels maintained
510 under current conditions.

511 This study also highlights an approach with potential interest for shellfisheries
512 industry affected by *Gymnodinium catenatum* blooms, as lower seawater pH may
513 promote elimination of PSTs. Although further studies are needed to confirm this

514 hypothesis and to set the optimal parameters to promote such elimination without
515 conditioning shellfish shell growth and well-being in future depuration facilities.

516

517 Acknowledgements

518 This study was supported by CERES project (European Union's Seventh Framework
519 Programme - FP7 /2007-2013). Ana C. Braga has a Doctoral Grant
520 (PD/BD/113484/2015) from the Portuguese Science and Technology Foundation (FCT).
521 António Marques and Pedro R. Costa are supported through the FCT Investigator
522 program (IF). This work contributes to project UID/Multi/04326/2013 from the
523 Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT). Thanks are due for the
524 financial support to CESAM (UID/AMB/50017 - POCI-01-0145-FEDER-007638), to
525 FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC), and the co-funding by the FEDER,
526 within the PT2020 Partnership Agreement and Compete 2020.

527

528

529

530

531

532

533

534

535 References

536

- 537 Alava, J.J., Cheung, W.W.L., Ross, P.S., Sumaila, U.R., 2017. Climate change-
538 contaminant interactions in marine food webs: Toward a conceptual framework.
539 *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 23, 3984–4001. doi:10.1111/gcb.13667
- 540 Anacleto, P., Maulvault, A.L., Lopes, V.M., Repolho, T., Diniz, M., Nunes, M.L.,
541 Marques, A., Rosa, R., 2014. Ecophysiology of native and alien-invasive clams in
542 an ocean warming context. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. -Part A Mol. Integr. Physiol.*
543 175, 28–37. doi:10.1016/j.cbpa.2014.05.003
- 544 Anestis, A., Lazou, A., Pörtner, H.O., Michaelidis, B., 2007. Behavioral, metabolic, and
545 molecular stress responses of marine bivalve *Mytilus galloprovincialis* during
546 long-term acclimation at increasing ambient temperature. *Am. J. Physiol. Integr.*
547 *Comp. Physiol.* 293, 911–921. doi:10.1152/ajpregu.00124.2007
- 548 Anestis, A., Pörtner, H.O., Karagiannis, D., Angelidis, P., Staikou, A., Michaelidis, B.,
549 2010. Response of *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (L.) to increasing seawater
550 temperature and to martellosis: Metabolic and physiological parameters. *Comp.*
551 *Biochem. Physiol. Part A Mol. Integr. Physiol.* 156, 57–66.
552 doi:10.1016/j.cbpa.2009.12.018
- 553 Areekijseree, M., Engkagul, A., Kovitvadhi, U., Thongpan, A., Mingmuang, M.,
554 Pakkong, P., Rungruangsak-Torrissen, K., 2004. Temperature and pH
555 characteristics of amylase and proteinase of adult freshwater pearl mussel,
556 *Hyriopsis (Hyriopsis) bialatus* Simpson 1900. *Aquaculture* 234, 575–587.
- 557 Bakun, A., Black, B.A., Bograd, S.J., García-Reyes, M., Miller, A.J., Rykaczewski,
558 R.R., Sydeman, W.J., 2015. Anticipated Effects of Climate Change on Coastal

559 Upwelling Ecosystems. *Curr. Clim. Chang. Reports* 1, 85–93. doi:10.1007/s40641-
560 015-0008-4

561 Banni, M., Hajer, A., Sforzini, S., Oliveri, C., Boussetta, H., Viarengo, A., 2014.
562 Transcriptional expression levels and biochemical markers of oxidative stress in
563 *Mytilus galloprovincialis* exposed to nickel and heat stress. *Comp. Biochem.*
564 *Physiol. Part C Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 160, 23–29. doi:10.1016/j.cbpc.2013.11.005

565 Bond, N.A., Cronin, M.F., Freeland, H., Mantua, N., 2015. Causes and impacts of the
566 2014 warm anomaly in the NE Pacific. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 42, 3414–3420.
567 doi:10.1002/2015GL063306

568 Botelho, M.J., Vale, C., Mota, A.M., Gonçalves, M. de L.S.S., 2010. Depuration
569 kinetics of paralytic shellfish toxins in *Mytilus galloprovincialis* exposed to
570 *Gymnodinium catenatum*: laboratory and field experiments. *J. Environ. Monit.* 12,
571 2269–2275. doi:10.1039/c0em00202j

572 Bricelj, V.M., Cembella, A.D., Laby, D., 2014. Temperature effects on kinetics of
573 paralytic shellfish toxin elimination in Atlantic surfclams, *Spisula solidissima*.
574 *Deep Sea Res. Part II Top. Stud. Oceanogr.* 103, 308–317.
575 doi:10.1016/j.dsr2.2013.05.014

576 Coppola, F., Almeida, Â., Henriques, B., Soares, A.M.V.M., Figueira, E., Pereira, E.,
577 Freitas, R., 2017. Biochemical impacts of Hg in *Mytilus galloprovincialis* under
578 present and predicted warming scenarios. *Sci. Total Environ.* 601–602, 1129–
579 1138. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.05.201

580 Costa, P.R., Pereira, P., Guilherme, S., Barata, M., Nicolau, L., Santos, M.A., Pacheco,
581 M., Pousão-Ferreira, P., 2012. Biotransformation modulation and genotoxicity in
582 white seabream upon exposure to paralytic shellfish toxins produced by

583 *Gymnodinium catenatum*. *Aquat. Toxicol.* 106–107, 42–47.
584 doi:10.1016/j.aquatox.2011.08.023

585 Dallas, L.J., Bean, T.P., Turner, A., Lyons, B.P., Jha, A.N., 2016. Exposure to tritiated
586 water at an elevated temperature: Genotoxic and transcriptomic effects in marine
587 mussels (*M. galloprovincialis*). *J. Environ. Radioact.* 164, 325–336.
588 doi:10.1016/j.jenvrad.2016.07.034

589 Doblin, M., Blackburn, S., Hallegraeff, G., 1999. Comparative study of selenium
590 requirements of three phytoplankton species: *Gymnodinium catenatum*,
591 *Alexandrium minutum* (Dinophyta) and *Chaetoceros* cf. *tenuissimus*
592 (*Bacillariophyta*). *J. Plankton Res.* 21, 1153–1169. doi:10.1093/plankt/21.6.1153

593 Duarte, C., Navarro, J.M.M., Acuña, K., Torres, R., Manríquez, P.H.H., Lardies,
594 M.A.A., Vargas, C.A.A., Lagos, N.A.A., Aguilera, V., 2014. Combined effects of
595 temperature and ocean acidification on the juvenile individuals of the mussel
596 *Mytilus chilensis*. *J. Sea Res.* 85, 308–314. doi:10.1016/j.seares.2013.06.002

597 EFSA, 2009. Scientific Opinion of the Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain on a
598 request from the European Commission on Marine Biotoxins in Shellfish –
599 Saxitoxin Group. *EFSA J.* 1019, 1–47.

600 Farrell, H., Seebacher, F., O’Connor, W., Zammit, A., Harwood, D.T., Murray, S.,
601 2015. Warm temperature acclimation impacts metabolism of paralytic shellfish
602 toxins from *Alexandrium minutum* in commercial oysters. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 21,
603 3402–3413. doi:10.1111/gcb.12952

604 Fernández-Reiriz, M., Range, P., Álvarez-Salgado, X., Espinosa, J., Labarta, U., 2012.
605 Tolerance of juvenile *Mytilus galloprovincialis* to experimental seawater
606 acidification. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 454, 65–74. doi:10.3354/meps09660

607 Filgueira, R., Guyondet, T., Comeau, L.A., Tremblay, R., 2016. Bivalve aquaculture-
608 environment interactions in the context of climate change. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 22,
609 3901–3913. doi:10.1111/gcb.13346

610 Fu, F., Tatters, A., Hutchins, D., 2012. Global change and the future of harmful algal
611 blooms in the ocean. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 470, 207–233. doi:10.3354/meps10047

612 Gobler, C.J., Doherty, O.M., Hattenrath-Lehmann, T.K., Griffith, A.W., Kang, Y.,
613 Litaker, R.W., 2017. Ocean warming since 1982 has expanded the niche of toxic
614 algal blooms in the North Atlantic and North Pacific oceans. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*
615 114, 4975–4980. doi:10.1073/pnas.1619575114

616 Hallegraeff, G.M., Blackburn, S.I., Doblin, M.A., Bolch, C.J.S., 2012. Global
617 toxicology, ecophysiology and population relationships of the chainforming PST
618 dinoflagellate *Gymnodinium catenatum*. *Harmful Algae* 14, 130–143.
619 doi:10.1016/j.hal.2011.10.018

620 Hu, M., Li, L., Sui, Y., Li, J., Wang, Y., Lu, W., Dupont, S., 2015. Effect of pH and
621 temperature on antioxidant responses of the thick shell mussel *Mytilus coruscus*.
622 *Fish Shellfish Immunol.* 46, 573–583. doi:10.1016/j.fsi.2015.07.025

623 IPCC, 2013. *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of*
624 *Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel*
625 *on Climate Change.* Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and
626 New York, NY, USA. doi:10.1017/CBO9781107415324

627 Kodama, M., 2010. *Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning Toxins: Biochemistry and Origin.*
628 *Aqua-BioScience Monogr.* 3, 1–38. doi:10.5047/absm.2010.00301.0001

629 Li, A.M.Y., Yu, P.K.N., Hsieh, D.P.H., Wang, W.-X., Wu, R.S.S., Lam, P.K.S., 2005.

630 Uptake and depuration of paralytic shellfish toxins in the green-lipped mussel,
631 *Perna viridis*: A dynamic model. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 24, 129–135.
632 doi:10.1897/03-397.1

633 Lischka, S., Udenbender, J., Boxhammer, T., Riebesell, U., 2011. Impact of ocean
634 acidification and elevated temperatures on early juveniles of the polar shelled
635 pteropod *Limacina helicina*: mortality, shell degradation, and shell growth.
636 *Biogeosciences* 8, 919–932. doi:10.5194/bg-8-919-2011

637 Lopes, V.M., Baptista, M., Repolho, T., Rosa, R., Costa, P.R., 2014. Uptake, transfer
638 and elimination kinetics of paralytic shellfish toxins in common octopus (*Octopus*
639 *vulgaris*). *Aquat. Toxicol.* 146, 205–211.

640 McCabe, R.M., Hickey, B.M., Kudela, R.M., Lefebvre, K.A., Adams, N.G., Bill, B.D.,
641 Gulland, F.M.D., Thomson, R.E., Cochlan, W.P., Trainer, V.L., 2016. An
642 unprecedented coastwide toxic algal bloom linked to anomalous ocean conditions.
643 *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 43, 10,366-10,376. doi:10.1002/2016GL070023

644 Michaelidis, B., Ouzounis, C., Paleras, A., Pörtner, H.H.O.H., 2005. Effects of long-
645 term moderate hypercapnia on acid-base balance and growth rate in marine
646 mussels *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 293, 109–118.
647 doi:10.3354/meps293109

648 Múgica, M., Izagirre, U., Marigómez, I., 2015. Lysosomal responses to heat-shock of
649 seasonal temperature extremes in Cd-exposed mussels. *Aquat. Toxicol.* 164, 99–
650 107. doi:10.1016/j.aquatox.2015.04.020

651 Nikinmaa, M., Anttila, K., 2015. 3. Responses of marine animals to ocean acidification,
652 in: Botana, L.M., Louzao, C., Vilariño, N. (Eds.), *Climate Change and Marine and*
653 *Freshwater Toxins*. DE GRUYTER, Berlin, München, Boston, p. 99–123.

654 doi:10.1515/9783110333596-005

655 Parker, L., Ross, P., O'Connor, W., Pörtner, H., Scanes, E., Wright, J., 2013. Predicting
656 the Response of Molluscs to the Impact of Ocean Acidification. *Biology (Basel)*. 2,
657 651–692. doi:10.3390/biology2020651

658 Pérez, F.F., Padín, X.A., Pazos, Y., Gilcoto, M., Cabanas, M., Pardo, P.C., Doval, M.D.,
659 Farina-Busto, L., 2010. Plankton response to weakening of the Iberian coastal
660 upwelling. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 16, 1258–1267. doi:10.1111/j.1365-
661 2486.2009.02125.x

662 Pörtner, H.O., Peck, L., Somero, G., 2007. Thermal limits and adaptation in marine
663 Antarctic ectotherms: an integrative view. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* 362,
664 2233–2258. doi:10.1098/rstb.2006.1947

665 Sakamoto, S., Sato, S., Ogata, T., Kodama, M., 2000. Formation of intermediate
666 conjugates in the reductive transformation of gonyautoxins to saxitoxins by thiol
667 compounds. *Fish. Sci.* 66, 136–141. doi:10.1046/j.1444-2906.2000.00020.x

668 Sato, S., Sakai, R., Kodama, M., 2000. Identification of thioether intermediates in the
669 reductive transformation of gonyautoxins into saxitoxins by thiols. *Bioorg. Med.*
670 *Chem. Lett.* 10, 1787–1789. doi:10.1016/S0960-894X(00)00332-2

671 Shumway, S.E., van Egmond, H.P., Hurst, J.W., Bean, L.L., 1995. Management of
672 Shellfish Resources., in: Hallegraeff, G.M., Anderson, D.M., Cembella, A.D.
673 (Eds.), *Manual on Harmful Marine Microalgae*. IOC Manuals and Guides No. 33
674 UNESCO, p. 433.

675 Silva, T., Caeiro, M.F., Costa, P.R., Amorim, A., 2015. *Gymnodinium catenatum*
676 Graham isolated from the Portuguese coast: Toxin content and genetic

677 characterization. *Harmful Algae* 48, 94–104. doi:10.1016/j.hal.2015.07.008

678 Sokolova, I., Lannig, G., 2008. Interactive effects of metal pollution and temperature on
679 metabolism in aquatic ectotherms: implications of global climate change. *Clim.*
680 *Res.* 37, 181–201. doi:10.3354/cr00764

681 Sousa, R., Gutiérrez, J.L., Aldridge, D.C., 2009. Non-indigenous invasive bivalves as
682 ecosystem engineers. *Biol. Invasions* 11, 2367–2385. doi:10.1007/s10530-009-
683 9422-7

684 Tatters, A.O., Flewelling, L.J., Fu, F., Granholm, A.A., Hutchins, D.A., 2013. High
685 CO₂ promotes the production of paralytic shellfish poisoning toxins by
686 *Alexandrium catenella* from Southern California waters. *Harmful Algae* 30, 37–43.
687 doi:10.1016/j.hal.2013.08.007

688 Vidal, T., Calado, A.J., Moita, M.T., Cunha, M.R., 2017. Phytoplankton dynamics in
689 relation to seasonal variability and upwelling and relaxation patterns at the mouth
690 of Ria de Aveiro (West Iberian Margin) over a four-year period. *PLoS ONE* 12(5):
691 e0177237. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0177237>

692 Yu, K.N., Kwong, R.W.M., Wang, W.-X., Lam, P.K.S., 2007. Biokinetics of paralytic
693 shellfish toxins in the green-lipped mussel, *Perna viridis*. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 54,
694 1068–1071. doi:10.1016/j.marpolbul.2007.02.007

695

696 Figure captions

697

698 Figure 1. Design of mussels feeding experiments with toxic dinoflagellates
699 *Gymnodinium catenatum* under four environmental conditions (Tr1: 19 °C and 8.0 pH;
700 Tr2: 24 °C and 8.0 pH; Tr3: 19 °C and 7.6 pH; Tr4: 24 °C and 7.6 pH), showing
701 sampling dates during uptake (grey) and elimination (white) phases.

702

703 Figure 2. PST toxicity ($\mu\text{g STX eq. kg}^{-1}$, mean \pm SD) determined in mussels
704 exposed to toxic *Gymnodinium catenatum* during 5 days and to non-toxic diet during
705 the subsequent 10 days, under four environmental conditions (Tr1: 19 °C and 8.0 pH;
706 Tr2: 24 °C and 8.0 pH; Tr3: 19 °C and 7.6 pH; Tr4: 24 °C and 7.6 pH)

707

708 Figure 3. Concentration ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, mean \pm SD) of PSTs (C1+2, GTX5, dcNeo,
709 dcGTX2+3 and dcSTX) determined in mussels exposed to *Gymnodinium catenatum* at
710 day 1 (white bars) and 5 (black bars), under four environmental conditions (Tr1: 19 °C
711 and 8.0 pH; Tr2: 24 °C and 8.0 pH; Tr3: 19 °C and 7.6 pH; Tr4: 24 °C and 7.6 pH).
712 Values marked with an asterisk represent significant differences ($p < 0.05$) from current
713 conditions (vs. Tr1) within the same exposure time.

714

715 Figure 4. Elimination of the PSTs (C1+2, dcSTX, GTX5, dcNeo and
716 dcGTX2+3) in mussels under four environmental conditions (Tr1: 19 °C and 8.0 pH;
717 Tr2: 24 °C and 8.0 pH; Tr3: 19 °C and 7.6 pH; Tr4: 24 °C and 7.6 pH). Dots and error
718 bars represent experimental data; the coloured lines represent the output of the
719 simulation model ($C_m = C_{m0} e^{-k_{el} t}$).

720

